

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Impact of the intercropping system on the population trend and percentage infestation of certain cowpea arthropod pests with reference to the yield income

Mohamed, Abd Elrahman Amro¹; Ali, Mohamed Ali ²; Ahmed, M. A. Ibrahim²; Mohamed, H. A. Hassan³ and Samar, A. Said ²

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

²Zoology and Entomology Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt.

³Plant Pathology Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO Abstract

Article History

Received: 30/10/2025

Accepted: 23/11/2025

Keywords

Intercropping system, cowpea, sucking pests and *Etiella zinckenella*.

This manuscript was initiated to determine the impact of the intercropping system on the population trend and percentage infestation of certain arthropod pests attacking cowpea. The impact of the intercropping system on the yield income was of concern. The results revealed that intercropping cowpea with soybeans reduced both *Thrips tabaci* (Lindeman) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) and *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) populations, while *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) was present in high numbers. Intercropping cowpea with basil revealed a 20.74% reduction in the *Etiella zinckenella* (Treitschke) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) populations. Intercropping cowpea with soybean did not result in a distinct reduction in *E. zinckenella* larvae populations. The percentage infestation of *E. zinckenella* on green and dry cowpea pods was not affected by either intercropping system. Intercropping cowpea with basil can reduce *E. zinckenella* infestation on green seeds by 20.56%, whereas intercropping cowpea with soybean reduced the pest infestation on dry seeds by 4.94%. With respect to the yield loss, it can be noted that intercropping cowpea with soybean could decrease the yield loss compared with planting alone or intercropping with basil. The percentage infestation of *E. zinckenella* on green pods and green seeds showed a high value when cowpea was intercropped with basil. However, the yield loss recorded its lowest values when cowpea was intercropped with basil. Factors responsible for these findings may need further study in the future.

Introduction

Cowpea is one of the key sources of protein in the human diet, consumed in different forms, especially in developing countries that may not always have the means for animal protein in adequate quantities,

as a “food security crop” for populations that consume it, as a traditional staple food, and as a significant cash crop (Adebayo *et al.*, 2013). The most important cowpea arthropod pests that received attention included (1) sucking pests such as

Empoasca spp. Walsh (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae), *Thrips tabaci* (Lindeman) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae), *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), and *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) (Helaly *et al.*, 1982; Abdel-Alim, 1994; Anandmurthy *et al.*, 2018 and Wari *et al.*, 2021). (2) The Lima bean pod borer *Etiella zinckenella* (Treitschke) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) (Metwally, 1995 and Amro, 2004). Intercropping is a mixed cropping that involves growing two or more crops simultaneously in the same soil. The main motivation for growing two or more crops together could be to boost land productivity. As a result, intercropping can bring numerous benefits, including greater land use efficiency, nutrient capture, weed, pest, and disease management, and longer production cycles. Other benefits of intercropping include improved seed quality and water quality control by reducing the usage of inorganic N fertilizers and substituting them with legumes (Alla *et al.*, 2015).

Intercropping has been accepted as a measure for the integrated management of insect pests. Several authors have reported that insect pest populations are generally reduced in a polyculture system compared to a monoculture of different field crops, in addition to the increase in yield income. Several reports on this approach were done by Matteson, 1982; Mwamlima *et al.*, 2016; and Dingha *et al.*, 2021. Therefore, this manuscript was initiated to determine the impact of the intercropping system on the population trend and percentage infestation of certain

arthropod pests attacking cowpea. The impact of the intercropping system on the yield income was of concern.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental area:

Experiments were carried out at the experimental farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Assiut University, during the 2021 and 2022 cowpea growing seasons at (Ca. 1050 m²). The cowpea cultivar (Cream7) was cultivated on 7th April, in both seasons. Normal agricultural procedures were performed, and insecticide treatments were completely prevented.

2. Efficacy of the intercropping system on the incidence of cowpea leaves and pods of arthropod pests:

A separate area was cultivated by cowpea (Cream 7) and basil (*Ocimum basilicum* L.) in intercropped replicates. Four replicates (10.50 m²) of cowpea were examined. An additional four replicates (10.50 m²) were cultivated by the same cultivar and soybean (*Glycine max*) (L.) Merr Giza111 in intercropped replicates. Weekly samples of five cowpea leaves and five green and dry cowpea pods were taken randomly and transferred to the laboratory in muslin bags. Collected leaves were examined using a stereomicroscope, and the whitefly (Nymphs), thrips (Nymphs + adults), and *T. urticae* (Mobile stages) were counted. The collected pods were dissected. The numbers of *E. zinckenella* (Bores + larvae) were counted. Weekly percentages of increase and/or decrease in the targeted pests' numbers were calculated according to their mean numbers using the following equation, as recorded by Abdel-Galil *et al.* (2007), with some modification as follows:

Percentage of increase and/or decrease = $\frac{M-m}{M} \times 100$

Where:

M = Mean no. on treated (intercropped)

m = Mean no. on control (solo)

3. Yield loss percentages on the intercropped cowpea:

A special experiment was conducted to evaluate the yield loss in cowpea caused by *E. zinckenella* natural infestation under intercropping systems. Twenty-five mature dry cowpea pods were collected at harvesting/each replicate/intercropping system, transferred to the laboratory, and dissected and carefully examined to estimate the yield loss. Damaged and undamaged pods in each replicate were counted. In addition, damaged and undamaged seeds were weighed (4 replicates) to determine the weight loss caused by the natural infestation of this insect pest/each intercropping system.

Yield loss percentages (Yield loss% / 100 dry pods/cowpea intercropping system) were estimated by the equation used by Rahman *et al.* (2017) as follows:

$$\text{Yield loss \%} = \frac{\text{Weight of damaged cowpea seeds}}{\text{Total weight of cowpea seeds}} \times 100$$

4. Statistical analysis:

Data was statistically analyzed using the F-test; means were compared according to Duncan's multiple range tests as described by Steel *et al.* (1997). The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed, and subsequently, the means were compared using Duncan's multiple range tests at the 5% level of probability (Duncan, 1955). All the analyses were accomplished using the Costat (Version 6.400).

Results and Discussion

1. Efficacy of the intercropping system on the population of cowpea leaf arthropod pests:

1.1. *Bemisia tabaci*:

Data presented in Table (1) expressed the average numbers of *B. tabaci* nymphs on solely cowpea plantations and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons. Data revealed that the mean numbers of *B. tabaci* nymphs showed a similar population during both seasons of the study. During the entire period of study, this insect pest presented less than one individual/5 trifoliolate leaves/intercropping system. The test revealed 0.58, 0.46, and 0.63 individual/5 trifoliolate leaves for the Cream7 Solo, Cream7 + Soybean, and Cream7+Basil intercropping systems, respectively. Meanwhile, *B. tabaci* nymphs appeared in such low numbers that their population presented non-significant variations between the tested intercropping systems ($f = 2.32^{ns}$ and 0.11^{ns}) during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons, respectively. The highest numbers of *B. tabaci* were recorded on cowpea intercropped with basil than those recorded on a single plantation of cowpea or that intercropped with soybean. Volatiles emitted from basil could be responsible for attracting *B. tabaci* adults to nearby crops, especially basil.

1.2. *Thrips tabaci*:

The average numbers of *T. tabaci* on the leaves of the solely cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons are clarified in Table (2). The obtained data revealed that the population of *T. tabaci* showed a high significant decrease in its numbers when cowpea was intercropped with

soybean and basil in both seasons of study, and during the entire period of study, and presented 4.75 and 2.63 individuals/5 trifoliolate cowpea leaves when compared with that cultivated solely (6.46 individuals/5 trifoliolate cowpea leaves). Variations between the inspection months and between the intercropping systems showed highly significant values. Therefore, it can be concluded that intercropped cowpea with soybean and basil revealed a high reduction in *T. tabaci* populations.

1.3. *Tetranychus urticae*:

The average numbers of *T. urticae* on the leaves of the solely cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons are clarified in Table (3). The obtained data revealed that the population of *T. urticae* showed a high significant increase in its population when cowpea was intercropped with soybean and exhibited 14.33, 114.17, and 64.25 individuals/5 trifoliolate cowpea leaves during 2021, 2022, and during the entire period of study, respectively. Fewer numbers of *T. urticae* were recorded in the same periods when cowpea was intercropped with basil (8.67, 43.92, and 26.30 individuals/5 trifoliolate cowpea leaves, respectively). It is important to note that the pest populations were at their lowest numbers when cowpea was cultivated in a solo plantation. During the same periods, the pest recorded 0.75, 11.42,

and 6.09 individuals/5 trifoliolate cowpea leaves on the solo cultivated cowpea leaves, respectively. Variations between the inspection months and between the intercropping systems showed highly significant values. Therefore, it can be noted that intercropped cowpea with soybean and/or basil could increase the *T. urticae* population several times more than that cultivated in the solo plantation. This finding could be attributed to the preference of the pest for those host plants, especially soybean, which was reviewed as the most important host plant of *T. urticae*.

In this approach, several researchers used intercropping to avoid the hazards of damaging cowpea plantations by sucking arthropod pests. Several authors describe intercropping as an ancient and traditional agronomic practice that can be explained as a system where two or more crop species are grown in the same field at the same time during a growing season (Ofori and Stern, 1987, and Eskandari and Ghanbari, 2010). Others stated that this method is an important cultural practice in reducing pest problems in an agro-ecosystem (Konar *et al.*, 2010, and Vaiyapuri *et al.*, 2010).

Table (1): Average numbers of *Bemisia tabaci* on leaves of solely cowpea plantations and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Inspection Year	Inspection month	Mean No. 5 trifoliate cowpea leaves/intercropping system			
		Cream7(Solo)	Cream7 +Soybean	Cream7 +Basil	Mean ± SE
2021	May (2)	0.25b ± 0.25	0.00b ± 0.00	1.25a ± 0.25	0.50B ± 0.19
	June (5)	1.25a ± 0.25	1.25a ± 0.25	1.00a ± 0.00	1.17A ± 0.11
	July (5)	0.25b ± 0.25	0.00b ± 0.00	0.00b ± 0.00	0.08C ± 0.08
	Mean	0.58A ± 0.19	0.42A ± 0.19	0.75A ± 0.18	0.58 ± 0.06
2022	May (2)	0.00c ± 0.00	0.00c ± 0.00	0.00c ± 0.00	0.00B ± 0.00
	June (5)	1.25ab ± 0.25	1.00ab ± 0.58	1.50a ± 0.29	1.25A ± 0.22
	July (5)	0.50bc ± 0.29	0.50bc ± 0.29	0.00c ± 0.00	0.33B ± 0.14
	Mean	0.58A ± 0.19	0.50A ± 0.23	0.50A ± 0.23	0.53 ± 0.08
2021 and 2022	Grand Mean	0.58A ± 0.16	0.46A ± 0.19	0.63A ± 0.16	0.55 ± 0.05

Number of monthly samples 2021: F value: Between months = 24.97**; between intercropping systems = 2.32^{ns}; Months × intercropping systems = 5.52** - 2022: F value: Between months = 19.75**; between intercropping systems = 0.11^{ns}; Months × intercropping systems = 1.09^{ns} -- Averages having the same letter are not significant at the 5% level according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

Table (2): Average numbers of *Thrips tabaci* on leaves of solely cowpea plantations and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Inspection Year	Inspection month	Mean No. 5 trifoliate cowpea leaves/intercropping system			
		Cream7 (Solo)	Cream7 +Soybean	Cream7 +Basil	Mean ± SE
2021	May (2)	0.25f ± 0.25	6.00a ± 0.41	5.00b ± 0.41	3.75A ± 0.78
	June (5)	1.00ef ± 0.00	3.50 cd ± 0.29	2.75d ± 0.25	2.42B ± 0.34
	July (5)	1.75e ± 0.25	3.75c ± 0.48	0.25f ± 0.25	1.92B ± 0.47
	Mean	1.00C ± 0.21	4.42A ± 0.40	2.67B ± 0.61	2.70 ± 0.11
2022	May (2)	15.00b ± 1.00	7.25c ± 0.48	2.50e ± 0.29	8.25A ± 1.59
	June (5)	18.75a ± 0.48	5.00d ± 0.41	2.75e ± 0.25	8.83A ± 2.14
	July (5)	2.00e ± 0.00	3.00e ± 0.00	2.50e ± 0.29	2.50B ± 0.15
	Mean	11.92A ± 2.19	5.08B ± 0.56	2.58C ± 0.15	6.53 ± 0.15
2021&2022	Grand Mean	6.46A ± 1.04	4.75B ± 0.44	2.63C ± 0.31	4.62 ± 1.11

Number of monthly samples 2021: F value: Between months = 25.87**; between intercropping systems = 84.07**; Months × intercropping systems = 25.97** - 2022: F value: Between months = 185.18**; between intercropping systems = 352.79**; Months × intercropping systems = 113.49** - Averages having the same letter are not significant at the 5% level according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

Table (3): Average numbers of *Tetranychus urticae* on leaves of solely cowpea plantations and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Inspection Year	Inspection month	Mean No. 5 trifoliate cowpea leaves/intercropping system			
		Cream7 (Solo)	Cream7 +Soybean	Cream7 +Basil	Mean ± SE
2021	May (2)	0.50f ± 0.29	15.50b ± 0.65	6.00e ± 0.41	7.33B ± 1.88
	June (5)	1.00f ± 0.00	18.50a ± 0.65	5.75e ± 0.25	8.42A ± 2.24
	July (5)	0.75f ± 0.25	9.00d ± 0.00	14.25c ± 0.48	8.00AB ± 1.68
	Mean	0.75C ± 0.13	14.33A ± 1.23	8.67B ± 1.21	7.92 ± 0.14
2022	May (2)	17.50e ± 0.65	175.25a ± 0.25	90.75c ± 0.48	94.50A ± 19.43
	June (5)	16.25f ± 0.25	166.75b ± 0.48	35.00d ± 0.41	72.67B ± 20.19
	July (5)	0.50h ± 0.29	0.50h ± 0.29	6.00g ± 0.41	2.33C ± 0.80
	Mean	11.42C ± 2.34	114.17A ± 24.26	43.92B ± 10.61	56.50 ± 0.14
2021&2022	Grand Mean	6.09C ± 1.17	64.25A ± 12.69	26.30B ± 4.88	32.21 ± 17.05

Number of monthly samples 2021: F value: Between months = 5.28*; between intercropping systems = 823.58**; Months × intercropping systems = 6.08** - 2022: F value: Between months = 40353.34**; between intercropping systems = 47980.63**; Months × intercropping systems = 3609.75** - Averages having the same letter are not significant at the 5% level according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

2. Efficacy of the intercropping system on the population of *Etiella zinckenella* larvae on green and dry cowpea pods:

2.1. Green cowpea pods:

The average numbers of *E. zinckenella* larvae infesting the green pods on the solely cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons are presented in Table (4). The average number of *E. zinckenella* larvae recorded the highest values when cowpea was intercropped with soybean, with an average of 11.00, 15.13, and 13.07 larvae/5 green cowpea pods during 2021, 2022, and during the entire period of study, respectively. However, the lowest values were recorded when cowpea was intercropped with basil. Cowpea cultivated in the solo plantation occupied fewer numbers of the pest than that intercropped with basil and semi-equal numbers of that intercropped with soybean. In general, it can be recorded that intercropped cowpea with basil revealed a distinct reduction in the *E. zinckenella* populations. Therefore, intercropping cowpea with basil was the best method to reduce the average numbers of *E. zinckenella* larvae infesting the green pods.

2.2. Dry cowpea pods:

The average number of *E. zinckenella* larvae infesting dry pods on

the solely cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons is presented in Table (5). It is clear that the average number of *E. zinckenella*-infested dry pods on solely cowpea was recorded (14.75, 16.25, and 15.50 larvae/5 dry cowpea pods during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons and during the entire period of study, respectively). It showed similar values when cowpea was intercropped with soybean. On the other hand, *E. zinckenella* infested dry pods on cowpea intercropped with basil presented the highest values, with an average of 18.25, 19.50, and 18.88 larvae/5 dry cowpea pods during 2021, 2022, and during the entire period of study, respectively. Therefore, it can be concluded that intercropping cowpea with soybean and/or basil could not present a distinct reduction in *E. zinckenella* larvae populations infesting dry cowpea pods. In this approach, Matteson (1982) conducted research on the impacts of cereal intercropping and modest permethrin sprays on cowpea insect pests and their natural enemies over the previous two decades. His findings revealed that intercropping's pest management capability is diverse and depends on environmental circumstances, but intercropping should be included in integrated pest management systems as insecticide use is gradually reduced.

Table (4): Average numbers of *Etiella zinckenella* larvae infesting green pods on a single cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Inspection Year	Inspection month	Mean No. 5 green cowpea pods/intercropping system			
		Cream7 (Solo)	Cream7 Soybean	Cream7 +Basil	Mean ± SE
2021	July (4)	6.25d±0.25	3.00e±1.00	2.00e±0.58	3.75B±0.65
	August (5)	15.25b±0.85	19.00a±0.91	10.75c±0.75	15.00A±1.11
	Mean	10.75A±1.75	11.00A±3.09	6.38B±1.71	9.38±0.34
2022	July (4)	8.75c±0.25	7.50d±0.50	7.25d±0.25	7.83A±0.27
	August (5)	20.75b±0.48	22.75a±0.25	22.25a±0.25	21.92B±0.31
	Mean	14.75A±2.28	15.13A±2.89	14.75A±2.84	14.88±0.13
2021 and 2022	Grand Mean	12.75A±2.00	13.07A±2.97	10.57B±2.26	12.13±0.79

Number of monthly samples 2021: F value: Between months = 272.56**; between intercropping systems = 19.43**, Months × intercropping systems = 12.16**- 2022: F value: Between months = 2837.19**; between intercropping systems = 0.89^{ns}; Months × intercropping systems = 15.60** - Averages having the same letter are not significant at the 5% level according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

Table (5): Average numbers of *Etiella zinckenella* larvae infested dry pods solely on cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Inspection Year	Inspection month	Mean No. 5 dry cowpea pods/intercropping system			
		Cream7 (Solo)	Cream7 +Soybean	Cream7 +Basil	Mean ± SE
2021	July (4)	10.00c±0.41	7.25d±0.85	11.50c±0.96	9.58b±0.67
	August (5)	19.50b±0.29	23.00a±1.08	25.00a±0.41	22.50a±0.77
	Mean	14.75B±1.81	15.13B±3.04	18.25A±2.60	16.04±0.30
2022	July (4)	11.25d±0.63	4.50f±0.29	9.50e±0.29	8.42B±0.89
	August (5)	21.25c±0.25	27.75b±0.25	29.50a±0.29	26.17A±1.08
	Mean	16.25B±1.92	16.13B±4.40	19.50A±3.78	17.30±0.14
2021 and 2022	Grand Mean	15.50B±1.85	15.63B±3.70	18.88A±3.17	16.67±1.10

Number of monthly samples 2021: F value: Between months = 474.80**; between intercropping systems = 14.01**; Months × intercropping systems = 9.51** - 2022: F value: Between months = 3801.87**; between intercropping systems = 58.91**; Months × intercropping systems = 191.82** - Averages having the same letter are not significant at the 5% level according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

3. Efficacy of the intercropping system on *Etiella zinckenella* percent infestation on green and dry cowpea pods:

3.1. Green cowpea pods:

Percent infestation of *E. zinckenella* on green pods of solely cowpea plantations and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons was estimated in Table (6). Data revealed that the percent infestation of *E. zinckenella* on green pods was duplicated during the second season of

the study in terms of the tested intercropping systems. During the entire study period, the percent infestation of *E. zinckenella* on green pods of solely cowpea plantations and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil presented similar values with an average of 35.00, 36.32, and 35.00% infestation/5 green cowpea pods, respectively. Therefore, it can be concluded that the intercropping system had no effect on the percentage infestation of *E. zinckenella* on green cowpea pods.

Table (6): Percent infestation of *Etiella zinckenella* on green pods of solely cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Inspection Year	Inspection month	Pod infestation%/5 green cowpea pods/intercropping system			
		Cream7 (Solo)	Cream7 +Soybean	Cream7 +Basil	Mean ± SE
2021	July (4)	13.75d ±1.25	11.25d ±1.25	13.75d ±0.48	12.92B ± 0.66
	August (5)	35.00b ± 0.58	38.00a ±0.00	29.00c ±0.41	34.00A ± 1.15
	Mean	24.38A±4.07	24.63A±5.09	21.38B±2.90	23.46±0.34
2022	July (4)	26.25c ± 1.25	25.00c ±0.00	26.25c ±1.25	25.83B ± 0.56
	August (5)	65.00b ± 0.58	71.00a ±0.41	71.00a ±0.41	69.00A ± 0.89
	Mean	45.63B ± 7.35	48.00A±8.69	48.63A±8.48	47.42±0.35
2021 and 2022	Grand Mean	35.00A ± 5.69	36.32A±6.88	35.00A±5.69	35.44 ± 0.44

Number of monthly samples 2021: F value: Between months= 942.23**; between intercropping systems = 9.24**; Months × intercropping systems = 23.38** - 2022: F value: Between months = 3811.42**; between intercropping systems = 6.83**; Months × intercropping systems = 10.24** - Averages having the same letter are not significant at the 5% level according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

3.2. Dry cowpea pods:

The percentage infestation of *E. zinckenella* on dry pods of solely cowpea plantations and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022

growing seasons was estimated in Table (7). Data revealed that the percent infestation of *E. zinckenella* on dry pods presented similar values during both seasons of the study. During the entire study period, the percent infestation of

E. zinckenella on dry pods of solely cowpea plantations and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil presented similar values with an average of 50.26, 50.76, and 51.69%

infestation/5 dry cowpea pods, respectively. Therefore, it can be concluded that the intercropping system did not affect the percent infestation of *E. zinckenella* on dry cowpea pods.

Table (7): Percent infestation of *Etiella zinckenella* on dry pods of solely cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Inspection Year	Inspection month	Pod infestation%/5 dry cowpea pods/intercropping system			
		Cream7 (Solo)	Cream7 +Soybean	Cream7 +Basil	Mean ± SE
2021	July (4)	33.75d±1.25	46.25b±1.25	42.50c±1.44	40.83B±1.72
	August (5)	46.00b±0.41	54.00a±0.82	52.00a±0.58	50.67A±1.08
	Mean	39.88C±2.39	50.13A±1.62	47.25B±1.93	45.75±0.45
2022	July (4)	36.25c±1.25	23.75e±1.25	31.25d±1.25	30.42B±1.68
	August (5)	85.00a±0.58	79.00b±1.00	81.00b±0.71	81.67A±0.86
	Mean	60.63A±9.23	51.38C±10.47	56.13B±9.43	56.05±0.44
2021 and 2022	Grand Mean	50.26A±5.76	50.76A±5.99	51.69A±5.61	50.90±0.42

Number of monthly samples 2021: F value: Between months = 119.21**; between intercropping systems = 45.95**; Months × intercropping systems = 2.11ns - 2022: F value: Between months = 3339.24**; between intercropping systems = 36.27**; Months × intercropping systems = 5.19* - Averages having the same letter are not significant at the 5% level according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

4. Efficacy of the intercropping system on *Etiella zinckenella* percent infestation on green and dry cowpea seeds:

4.1. Green cowpea seeds:

Percent infestation of *E. zinckenella* on green seeds of solely cowpea plantations and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons was estimated in Table (8). Data revealed that the pest infestation on green seeds during the second season was 2.45,

2.14, and 2.13 times of that recorded during the first season on the tested intercropping systems, respectively. During the entire period of study, the percent infestation of *E. zinckenella* on green seeds of solely cowpea plantations and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil exhibited 13.67, 14.08, and 11.34% infestation/seeds of 5 green cowpea pods, respectively. Thus, it can be noted that intercropping cowpea with basil can reduce the pest infestation on green seeds.

Table (8): Percent infestation of *Etiella zinckenella* on green seeds of solely cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Inspection Year	Inspection Month	Seeds infestation%/5 green cowpea pods/intercropping system			
		Cream7 (Solo)	Cream7 +Soybean	Cream7 +Basil	Mean ± SE
2021	July (4)	3.92c±0.28	1.61d±0.15	2.15d±0.09	2.56B±0.31
	August (5)	11.92b±0.82	16.33a±0.23	12.33b±0.23	13.53A±0.66
	Mean	7.92B±1.56	8.97A±2.78	7.24B±1.93	8.05±0.16
2022	July (4)	4.83e±0.78	7.00d±0.00	5.17e±0.29	5.67B±0.38
	August (5)	33.98a±0.54	31.37b±0.59	25.68c±0.22	30.34A±1.07
	Mean	19.41A±5.52	19.19A±4.61	15.43B±3.88	18.01±0.20
2021 and 2022	Grand Mean	13.67A±3.53	14.08A±3.70	11.34B±2.90	13.03±0.86

Number of monthly samples 2021: F value: Between months = 1196.06**; between intercropping systems = 10.10**; Months × intercropping systems = 8.90** - 2022: F value: Between months = 3683.51**; between intercropping systems = 40.39**; Months × intercropping systems = 7.73** - Averages having the same letter are not significant at the 5% level according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

4.2. Dry cowpea seeds:

Percent infestation of *E. zinckenella* on dry seeds of solely cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons was estimated in Table (9). Percent infestation on dry cowpea seeds during the first season of study (2021) revealed much lower values than those presented during the second season (2022). As an average of both seasons (the entire

period of study), the highest percentage of *E. zinckenella* infestation was recorded when cowpea was intercropped with basil, by 25.12% infestation/seeds of 5 dry cowpea pods. However, the lowest value (22.92%) was recorded when cowpea was intercropped with soybean, followed by (23.87%) when cowpea was cultivated solely. Intercropping cowpea with basil did not reduce the pest infestation on dry seeds.

Table (9): Percent infestation of *Etiella zinckenella* on dry seeds of solely cowpea plantation and cowpea intercropped with soybean and basil in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Inspection Year	Inspection month	Seeds infestation%/5 dry cowpea pods/intercropping system			
		Cream7 (Solo)	Cream7 +Soybean	Cream7 +Basil	Mean ± SE
2021	July (4)	17.43d ± 0.91	14.00e ± 0.64	14.92e ± 0.42	15.45B ± 0.57
	August (5)	21.10c ± 0.10	23.63b ± 0.51	27.77a ± 0.66	24.17A ± 0.87
	Mean	19.27B ± 0.81	18.82B ± 1.86	21.35A ± 2.46	19.81 ± 0.23
2022	July (4)	11.00d ± 0.40	9.89de ± 0.46	8.77e ± 0.21	9.89B ± 0.34
	August (5)	45.93b ± 0.74	44.15c ± 0.61	49.00a ± 0.00	46.36A ± 0.67
	Mean	28.47A ± 6.61	27.02B ± 6.48	28.89A ± 7.60	28.13 ± 0.20
2021 and 2022	Grand Mean	23.87B ± 3.66	22.92C ± 4.16	25.12A ± 5.02	23.97 ± 0.64

Number of monthly samples 2021: F value: Between months = 371.66**; between intercropping systems = 11.86**; Months × intercropping systems = 35.31** - 2022: F value: Between months = 8310.01**; between intercropping systems = 7.96**; Months × intercropping systems = 22.27** - Averages having the same letter are not significant at the 5% level according to Duncan's multiple range tests.

5. Efficacy of the intercropping system on the percentage of increase or decrease of cowpea leaves and pod pests' population and percentage of infestation:

5.1. Leaves of arthropod pests:

The average numbers of the prevailing cowpea leaf pests of the tested intercropping systems and the population's percent of increase or decrease in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons were estimated in Table (10). The obtained data revealed that the populations of *B. tabaci* decreased by 28.89% when cowpea was intercropped with soybean, whereas they increased by 7.94% when cowpea was intercropped with basil. Onion thrips and *T. tabaci* populations decreased by 36.00% and 145.63% when cowpea was intercropped with soybean and basil, respectively. The TSSM *T. urticae* revealed the highest

increase of its populations in both intercropping systems, by 90.54% and 76.87%, when cowpea was intercropped with soybean and basil, respectively. Thus, it can be noted that the intercropping system can be a useful procedure when cowpea is intercropped with soybean and basil to control *B. tabaci* and *T. tabaci*. However, conversely, the results were found in accordance with *T. urticae*. Dingha *et al.* (2021) investigated whether cowpea intercropping increases the abundance and diversity of pollinators and other beneficial insects and crop yield while decreasing the abundance of the brown marmorated stink bug. Pollinator abundance and diversity were highest in the cowpea-intercropped treatments compared with the controls. The production of pollinator-dependent crops (PDCs) intercropped with cowpea resulted in more beneficial insects.

Their findings show that intercropping cowpeas with PDCs attract more and different pollinators, resulting in higher crop output. However, to optimize

pollination, planting dates that coincide with the blossoming of both cowpeas and PDCs should be considered.

Table (10): Average numbers of the prevailing cowpea leaf pests of the tested intercropping systems and the population's percent of increase or decrease in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Arthropod Pest	Mean no. 5 trifoliate cowpea leaves/intercropping system			
	Cowpea part	Cream7 (Solo)	Cream7 +Soybean	Cream7 +Basil
<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Cowpea leaves	0.58	0.45 (28.89)	0.63 (7.94)
<i>Thrips tabaci</i>		6.46	4.75 (36.00)	2.63(- 145.63)
<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>		6.08	64.25 (90.54)	26.29 (76.87)

Percentage of increase or decrease

5.2. Pods of arthropod pests:

The average numbers of *E. zinckenella*, percent infestation, and percent of increase or decrease/intercropping systems in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons were estimated in Table (11). On dry pods, this insect pest population increased by 0.83% and 17.90% when cowpea was intercropped with soybean and basil, respectively. This finding could be attributed to the attraction of *E. zinckenella* moths to basil volatiles during the cowpea budding period. Percent infestation of *E. zinckenella* on green and dry pods showed no or negligible values of increase in the pest populations, ranging between 3.61 and 0.99% when cowpea was intercropped with soybean. However, the percentage of infestation ranged between 0.00 and 2.79% when cowpea was intercropped with basil. Percent infestation of *E. zinckenella* on green seeds revealed a significant decrease (20.56%) when cowpea was intercropped with basil and (4.14%) in dry seeds when cowpea was

intercropped with soybeans. Thus, it can be concluded that the impact of the intercropping system on *E. zinckenella* populations and percent infestation showed variable values of increase or decrease according to the host plant part and the intercropping system. The average number of *E. zinckenella* on green pods and the percentage infestation on green seeds showed high values when cowpea was intercropped with basil. Mwamlima *et al.* (2016) investigated the impact of intercropping and foliar insecticides used to manage cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) pests on cowpea pests. The results showed that the intercropped cowpea treatments at the three sites had similar pest levels to those obtained from solely sprayed cowpea. Delaying cowpea seeding reduced *Maruca testulalis* (Geyer) (Lepidoptera: Crambidae) and *Anoplocnemis curvipes* (Fabricius) (Hemiptera: Coreidae) damage but increased thrips damage in Bunda (One of seven districts in the Mara Region, Tanzania).

Table (11): Average numbers of *Etiella zinckenella* percent infestation, and percent of increase or decrease/intercropping systems in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons.

Arthropod Pest	Average number/5 cowpea pods and percentage of increase and decrease/Intercropping system			
	Cowpea part	Cream7 (Solo)	Cream 7 + Soybean	Cream 7 + Basil
<i>Etiella zinckenella</i>	Average number on green pods	12.75	13.06 (2.37)	10.56 (20.74)
	Average number on dry pods	15.50	15.63 (0.83)	18.88 (17.90)
	Percent infestation of green pods	35.00	36.31 (3.61)	35.00 (0.00)
	Percent infestation on dry pods	50.25	50.75 (0.99)	51.69 (2.79)
	Percent infestation of green seeds	13.66	14.08 (2.98)	11.33 (-20.56)
	Percent infestation of dry seeds	23.87	22.92 (4.14)	25.11 (4.94)

Percentage of increase or decrease

6. Yield loss percentages on the intercropped cowpea:

The efficiency of intercropping cowpea with soybean and basil on the yield loss percentage of cowpea seeds caused by *E. zinckenella* in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons was estimated in Table (12). Data revealed that the highest loss in the yield income was recorded when cowpea was intercropped with basil (43.41%), followed by 36.42% and 34.51% when cowpea was planted alone and with soybean, respectively. Therefore, it can be noted that intercropping cowpea with basil could decrease the yield loss compared with planting alone or intercropping with soybean.

This finding has been supported by some authors. They reported that

Table (12): Efficiency of intercropping cowpea with soybean and basil on the weight loss percentage of cowpea seeds caused by *Etiella zinckenella* in Assiut during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons

Intercropping system	Yield loss %/100 dry pods/Cowpea intercropping system			
	2021	2022	Mean ±SE	RO
Cream7 (Solo)	35.25b ± 1.11	37.59b ± 0.49	36.42B ± 0.68	2
Cream 7 + Soybean	34.84b ± 0.16	34.17c ± 0.98	34.51C ± 0.55	3
Cream7 +Basil	42.50a ± 0.50	44.32a ± 0.49	43.41A ± 0.32	1

2021: F value: between treatments = 58.50**; 2022: F value: between treatments = 44.45**. Averages having the same letter are not significant at the 5% level according to Duncan's multiple range tests. RO = Ranking order

References

- Abdel-Alim, A. (1994):** Ecological studies on certain insects infesting cowpea plants in mini region. *Minia Journal of Agricultural Research and Development (Egypt)*, 16(2): 261-273.
- Abdel-Galil, F. A.; Amro, M. A. and Abdel-Moniem, A. S. H. (2007):** Effect of drought stress on the incidence of certain arthropod pests and predators inhabiting cowpea plantations *Archives of Phytopathology and Plant Protection*, 40 (3): 207-214. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03235400500424570>
- Adebayo, R.A.; Idoko, J.E. and Adetuyi, R.O. (2013):** Response of

intercropping is an important method to increase the total yield per unit area. The system of intercropping was especially adopted in countries where the acreage preserved for special crops is relatively limited. It is expected that intercropping two crops of widely different needs for the ecological conditions might increase the total combined yields. This is fully indicated when maize, as a tall plant, is intercropped with short cowpea plants (Dissemond and Hindorf, 1990). Silva *et al.* (2020) the aim of their study was to identify maize and cowpea cultivars that can be grown as mono-crops or intercrops to produce green grain. They reported that monocots were superior to the intercrops for green-ear, green-pod, and green-grain yield.

- four local varieties of cowpea to the water extracts of *Chromolaena odorata* (King and Robinson) and *Vernonia amygdalina* (L.). *IJAFS*,4(6):447-456.
- Alla, W. H.; Shalaby, E. M.; Dawood, R. A. and Zohry, A. A. (2015):** Effect of cowpea (*Vigna sinensis* L.) with maize (*Zea mays* L.) intercropping on yield and its components *International Journal of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering*, 8(11): 1258-1264.
- Amro, M.A. (2004):** The influence of plant characteristics on the field infestation and resistance status of certain cowpea cultivars to the lima bean pod borer *Etiella zinckenella* Treitschke and the southern cowpea

- weevil *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius). The 2nd International Conference For Development and Environment in the Arab World, March 23-25: 375-384.
- Anandmurthy, T.; Parmar, G. M. and Arvindarajan, G. (2018):** Seasonal incidence of major sucking pests infesting cowpea and their relation to weather parameters International Journal of Plant Protection, 11(1): 35-38. doi:10.15740/HAS/IJPP/11.1/35-38
- Dingha, B. N.; Omaliko, P. C.; Amoah, B. A.; Jackai, L. E. and Shrestha, D. (2021):** Evaluation of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) in an intercropping system as a pollinator enhancer for increased crop yield, 13(17): 9612. doi:10.3390/su13179612
- Dissemond, A. and Hindorf, H. (1990):** Influence of sorghum/maize/cowpea intercropping on the insect situation in mbita/kenya. Journal of Applied Entomology, 109 (1-5): 144-150.
- Duncan, D. B. (1955):** Multiple range and multiple F tests. Biometrics, 11(1): 1-42. https://doi.org/10.2307/3001478
- Eskandari, H. and Ghanbari, A. (2010):** Effect of different planting patterns of wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) and bean (*Vicia faba*) on grain yield, dry matter production and weed biomass. Notulae Scientia Biologicae, 2(4): 111-115. doi:10.15835/nsb244824
- Helaly, M. M.; Ibrahim, A. E. and Saleh, M. R. A. (1982):** Fluctuations in the population densities of *Empoasca* sp., *Aphis craccivora* Koch, and *Tetranychus arabicus* Attiah attacking cowpea plants at Zagazig, Egypt. Bulletin de la Societe Entomologique d'Egypte, 64: 35-43.
- Konar, A.; Singh, N. J. and Paul, R. (2010):** Influence of intercropping on the population dynamics of major insect pests and vectors of potato. Journal of Entomological Research, 34(2): 151-154.
- Matteson, P.C. (1982):** The effects of intercropping with cereals and minimal permethrin applications on the insect pests of cowpea and their natural enemies in Nigeria. Tropical Pest Management, 28(4), 372–380. https://doi.org/10.1080/09670878209370743
- Metwally, S. A. (1995):** Effect of planting date and certain climatic factors on the fluctuation of *Etiella zinckenella* Treit. Infesting cowpea in qualia governorate. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 71: 1-7.
- Mwamlima, L. H.; Kabambe, V. H.; Nyirenda, G. K. C. and Mhango, W. G. (2016):** Effects of intercropping systems and foliar pesticides applied to control cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L) pests on the incidence of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) pests Agricultural Science Research Journal, 6(12): 313–321.
- Ofori, F. and Stern, W.R. (1987):** Cereal–legume intercropping systems. Advances in agronomy, 41: 41-90. https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113(08)60802-0
- Rahman, T.; Liu, X.; Hussain, S.; Ahmed, S.; Chen, G.; Yang, F.; Chen, L.; Du, J.; Liu, W.; and Yang, W. (2017):** Water use efficiency and evapotranspiration in maize-soybean relay strip intercrop systems as affected by planting geometries. Plos One, 12(6). https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0178332
- Silva, M. A. L. D.; Lima E.; Silva, P. S. L.; Oliveira, V. R. D.; Sousa, R. P. D. and Silva, P. I. B. (2020):** Intercropping maize and cowpea cultivars: I. Green grain yield.

- Revista Ciência Agronômica, 51: e20186552.
- Steel, R. G. D.; Torrie, J. H. and Dicky, D. A. (1997): Principles and procedures of statistics.** A biometrical approach (3rd ed), (352-358). New York : McGraw-Hill.
- Vaiyapuri, K.; Amanullah, M. M.; Rajendran, K. and Sathyamoorthi, K. (2010):** Intercropping unconventional green manures in cotton: An organic approach for multiple benefits: A review. Asian Journal of Plant Sciences, 9(4): 223-226.
- Wari, D.; Kuramitsu, K. and Kavallieratos, N. G. (2021):** Sap-sucking pests.; they do matter. Insects, 12(4): 363. doi: 10.3390/insects12040363